

Effects of Hybridization of Cow Hooves and Bamboo Fibres on the Microstructural, Physical and Tribological Properties of Fabricated Brake Pads

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Abstract

The effects of hybridization of cow hooves and bamboo fibres on the microstructural, physical and tribological properties of fabricated brake pads was investigated. Nine (9) different sample formulations - (01 = formulation without bamboo fibre; 02 = formulation without cow hooves filler; and 1 – 7 = formulations with combined varying amounts of cow hooves filler and bamboo fibre) were developed and fabricated using compression moulding technique. The microstructural, physical, and tribological properties of the fabricated brake pads samples were evaluated. In respect of the microstructural properties, the distribution of constituent materials in the samples were found to be uneven. However, they are relatively compact. The densities of brake pad samples (1 - 7) show that they are higher than the minimum threshold of 1.0 g/cm³. As expected, sample 7 with higher proportion of bamboo fibre than cow hoof gave the highest water and oil absorptions. Considering the effect of varying proportion of cow hoof and bamboo fibre on the tribological properties of the fabricated brake pad samples, both the static and dynamic coefficients of friction increased from sample 1 to sample 6, and then showed a marked decrease with sample 7. With respect to wear rate determination, sample 7 with higher proportion of bamboo fibre than cow hoof gave the lowest wear rate (1.026E-08 g/m).

Keywords: Cow hooves, Bamboo fibres, Brake pads, Coefficient of friction, Wear rate.

Introduction

The use of friction to control motion is an essential safety feature in the operation of aircraft, automobiles, and many other machines. This safety measure is usually achieved through reducing the motion of the rolling parts of the object on motion. In automobile, for example, the tires are the observable rolling parts that move an entire vehicle and the application of a braking system on the wheels of the tire of a moving vehicle can cause deceleration, stopping, and maintain a required speed or keep the vehicle at a standstill (Kumar and Suman, 2017). The friction materials could be organic such as cellulose, rubber, and resins, offering a good balance of performance and cost (Pinca-Bretotean et al., 2019). The friction materials could also be semi-metallic which contains a higher percentage of metal like steel wool, wire, and copper along with organic materials, offering good stopping power and heat dissipation. Additionally, the friction materials could be ceramic made from ceramic fibres, fillers, and binding resins. The reinforcing materials add strength and help the brake pads withstand the high temperatures and pressures during braking. Reinforcing fibres and fillers in brake pads primarily enhance performance characteristics such as friction, wear resistance, and thermal stability as well as improve manufacturability and reduce costs. Traditionally, synthetic reinforcing fibres such as aramid fibres (like Kevlar) and basalt fibres which provide good strength and wear resistance are used. However, recently, natural reinforcing fibres including coconut fibre, bamboo fibre, flax fibre, hemp fibre, jute fibre, sisal fibre, banana fibre, and kenaf fibre among others are increasingly being explored due to their sustainability and lower cost. These fibres enhance the mechanical properties and influence frictional characteristics.

The use of natural fillers in friction materials is owing to their inherent chemical and structural properties. Thus, bamboo (*Dendrocalmus Strictus*) fillers in composite preparation are primarily used due to cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin composition, which are responsible for its strength. Bamboo fillers exhibit favourable physical properties including low density, biodegradability, acoustic insulation, and low thermal conductivity, making them a sustainable and advantageous alternative to traditional materials in various composite applications. Moreso, bamboo possesses excellent mechanical properties, including high compressive strength (averaging 217 kg/cm²), shear strength (averaging 55 kg/cm²), and tensile strength (averaging 2123 kg/cm²) (Hartono et al., 2022). Its mechanical strength is influenced by physical and anatomical characteristics, such as the presence of vascular bundles, density, and moisture content. In view of this, Bhonde et al., (2014) studied the physical and mechanical properties of bamboo with a view to understanding its viability for use as reinforcement materials for structural design. The study revealed that bamboo has desired properties that could be harnessed to design eco-friendly structural components. Purboputro et al., (2018) studied the utilisation of bamboo fibre as a filler material for brake pad lining. Using different proportions of the fibre, and varying the various additives, the study revealed that the formulation with the highest proportion of bamboo fibre (40 %) and polyester (40 %) has the highest hardness of 14.47 BHN, and the value exceeds that of existing materials (13.7 BHN) by 7.4%.

In a related study, Bala et al, (2016) conducted a study to analyse the potential of harnessing cow hooves as filler material in automobile brake lining. In the study, X-ray fluorescence analysis was conducted to determine the elemental composition of cow hooves as a viable filler material. The study also revealed the presence of other elements in cow hooves such as potassium, iron, zirconium, zinc which have been reported to depict desired characteristics when used as friction materials.

Despite the advantages of single natural fillers used in composite preparation for brake pads application, some studies have reported the remarkable impact of hybrid fillers for excellent physical, chemical, mechanical and tribological performance of brake pads (Egeonu et al., 2015). Hence, Sutikno et al., (2018) used bamboo fibre and coconut to create a non-asbestos brake pad material. They also employed alumina, epoxy resin, and magnesium oxide in their study. The brake pad samples were produced at temperature of 200°C for 20 min under a 1000kg compression load. The non-asbestos brake pads made of bamboo fibre, epoxy, magnesium oxide, and aluminium oxide with a composition of 29%, 40%, 6%, and 25%, respectively, had a hardness of 37.14 HRB, temperature resistance of 251.53 °C, a friction coefficient of 0.454, and a wear rate of 0.323 mm³/N·mm, accordingly. However, the brake pads made of 20 % coconut fibre, 46 % epoxy, 6 % magnesium oxide, and 28 % aluminium oxide, had a hardness of 44.10 HRB, temperature resistance of 250.56 °C, a friction coefficient of 0.46, and a wear rate of 0.242 mm³/N·mm. The wear rate and friction coefficient of bamboo fibre-reinforced composite brake pads were observed to be comparable to commercial brake pads.

Additionally, Simamora et al., (2020) studied the mechanical properties of brake pad made from a combination of candlenut shell and coconut shell. Water absorption, hardness, wear rate and morphology of the composites were investigated. The obtained results show that sample S-03 with a lower proportion of candlenut shell powder and coconut shell powder with a higher proportion of iron sand, pineapple leaf fibre and carbon exhibited the desired hardness of 92 HRK, wear resistance of 3.67 x 10⁻⁵ g/mm².s, and water absorption of 5.84 x 10⁻³ %. Similarly, Adeyemi et al., (2016) evaluated the combined use of cocoa beans shell, maize husk and palm kernel shell for composite preparation for brake pad application. Results showed that friction coefficient, abrasion resistance and water absorption decreased as weight percent of the formulation increased while compressive strength and tensile strength increased with increase in weight percent of the formulation. The present study seeks to investigate the effects of hybridization of cow hooves and bamboo fibres on the microstructural, physical and tribological properties of phenolic-based brake pads.

Experimental procedure

Materials

The natural fillers used were sourced from cow hooves and bamboo fibres procured from abattoir at Obinze and Naze timber market Owerri, respectively. Aluminium oxide was used as an abrasive, while graphite was used a friction modifier. Barium sulphate was used as a wear resistant material and phenolic resin was used as a binder to hold all other constituents together.

Method

Processing of cow hooves and bamboo wood

The unpulverized cow hooves were washed three times with warm water to remove adhering dirty particles. Then, they were sun-dried for four days to make them brittle for easier crushing. The sun-dried cow hooves were dried in a thermostatic oven for three (3) hours at 250°C to remove contaminating oil. The resulting cow hooves were placed in a furnace set at 306°C and later retrieved after the volatile organic compounds have been given off.

The dried cow hooves were cut into pieces using a hand-held axe, and later crushed in a mortar using a pestle. The crushed cow hooves were further pulverized to powdered form using a conventional ball milling machine. The obtained cow hooves powder was then sieved using a 100 μm mesh sieve. The 100 μm mesh sieve was confirmed to be the optimum size for the production of brake pad (Adekunle, et al., 2020).

Similarly, a few lengths of dry bamboo wood were procured and into short lengths of 2 m. Then they were first milled using the conventional wood milling machine through the circular surface to obtain fine bamboo fibres. The resulting bamboo fibres were pulverized using a ball milling machine. They were collected and oven-dried for three (3) hours at 150°C. The oven-dried bamboo fibres were then sieved using a 100 μm mesh sieve.

Characterization of the pulverized cow hooves and bamboo fibres

Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectroscopy Analysis

The FTIR spectra of the cow hoof and bamboo fillers were acquired in the range of 450–4000 cm^{-1} wavenumber by use of PerkinElmer Spectrum IR spectrophotometer, version 10.7.2. The procedure involved mixing 4 mg each of the cow hoof and bamboo sample with 100 mg of pure anhydrous KBr. The mixture was ground to fine powdered form using a mortar and a pestle. The ground mixture was then placed onto a circular disk and pressed into a transparent flake. Subsequently, it was placed into the detection chamber of IR spectrophotometer with a sample holder, and the IR spectra were recorded with the Omnic software at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , with 64 scans and a gain of 1.

Gas Chromatography – Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis

The GC–MS analysis was performed using a gas chromatograph equipped with an autosampler and a mass-selective detector (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA). The capillary column used was HP-5MS, 30 m \times 0.25 mm \times 0.25 mm, from Agilent (Santa Clara, CA, USA). Helium was used as carrier gas at 1.5 mL/min. The split–splitless injector was operated in pulsed pressure splitless mode as follows: initial pressure 0.2 MPa (30 p.s.i.) for 1.3 min, decreased to constant flow. The purge valve was opened after 1.5 min. The injection volume was 5 μL . The temperatures of the GC system were set as follows: injector temperature 290 °C; transfer line temperature 280 °C; oven temperature program: 50 °C (1.5 min)–30 °C/min–180 °C–20 °C/min–280 °C (20 min). MS detector (quadrupole) was operated in the EI mode at 70 eV with a mass scan range of 50–450 m/z and the sampling rate of 3.6 scans/s.

Preparation and fabrication of brake pad samples

The brake pad samples fabrication was based on the formulation given in Table 1. Each sample formulation was prepared using a compression moulding machine at a mould temperature of 130°C and clamping pressure of 100 psi. After compression-moulding, each sample was post-cured for 5 minutes, removed and air-dried for 2 hours before placing in the desiccator prior to characterization.

Table 1: The composite formulations for brake pad samples fabrication

Materials	Sample ID								
	01	02	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Cow hooves (%wt.)	10	-	8	7	6	5	4	3	2
Bambo fibre (%wt.)	-	10	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Phenolic Resin (%wt.)	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70	70
Aluminium Oxide (%wt.)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Graphite (%wt.)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Barium Sulphate (%wt.)	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10

where 01 represents formulation without bamboo fibre, 02 represents formulation without cow hooves filler, and 1 – 7 represents formulations with varying amounts of cow hooves filler and bamboo fibre.

Characterizations of the fabricated brake pad samples

Microstructure analysis using Advanced Optical Microscope

Microstructure analysis of brake pad linings is a critical evaluation that provides insights into the material's internal structure, including the spatial dispersion of the constituent materials, size, shape, and composition of the phases and constituents that make up the brake pad lining. This analysis helps in understanding how the material's microstructural characteristics influence its performance, such as its frictional properties, wear resistance, and thermal stability.

Thus, a small section of the brake pad lining was cut for examination under the microscope. The mounted sample was polished using a series of abrasive papers and diamond pastes, progressing from coarse to fine grit, to achieve a mirror-like surface finish. This step was crucial as it ensured that the internal structure was observed without interference from surface imperfections. The polished sample was etched using a sodium hydroxide solution to reveal the microstructure. The advanced software in the optical microscope was used to reveal the microstructural features such as size, shape, distribution of constituent materials, and pores observed under the microscope. The presence of pores and voids within the microstructure is critical for assessing the material's performance. thus, high porosity can lead to reduced mechanical strength and increased wear.

Physical properties tests

The density test for a brake pad lining helps in assessing the compactness and consistency of the material, which are critical factors in ensuring the brake pad lining's performance, durability, and safety. Thus, a small rectangular-shaped sample was cut and weighed using an electronic weighing balance in gram. Thereafter, the length, width and thickness of the sample were measured in

centimetre (cm) using a vernier calliper. The volume of the sample was determined by multiplying the length, width and thickness. Hence, the density of each formulation was determined by dividing the mass of the sample by its volume as given in equation (1).

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Mass of brake pad sample}}{\text{Volume of brake pad sample}} \quad (1)$$

The water and oil absorption tests for brake linings are essential quality control procedures to evaluate how a brake lining material responds when exposed to water and oil. These tests help determine the brake lining's ability to resist deterioration and maintain its frictional properties in the presence of these substances, which could be encountered during real-world vehicle operation.

The water and oil absorption of each sample was determined by soaking the sample in water and engine oil for 24 hours (1 day), respectively. Prior to the test, each sample was oven-dried and weight measured. The samples were cleaned after 24 hours in water and oil (engine oil), and weight taken thereafter. The percentage absorption of water and oil was estimated using the equation (2) according to Idris et al., (2015):

$$\text{Absorption} = \frac{W_1 - W_0}{W_0} \times 100 \% \quad (2)$$

where W_0 = Weight (g) of sample before immersion, W_1 = Weight (g) of sample after immersion.

A high percentage of water or oil absorption indicates that the brake pad lining material is prone to absorbing fluid, which could negatively impact its performance. Therefore, materials with low water absorption are preferred for brake linings to ensure consistent performance in wet conditions.

Tribological properties test

The coefficient of friction (often denoted by the symbol μ) was determined using a friction testing machine. Here, a clean horizontal plane surface was obtained. A test brake pad sample was affixed to a flat sled (or block), and then placed on the clean horizontal plane surface. A mass of 10 g was placed on the sled affixed to the brake pad sample (normal force, N). A force-measuring device was attached to the sled affixed to the brake pad. Incremental horizontal force was applied to pull the brake pad-sled-normal load assembly system until it began to move. The values of the maximum static frictional forces (F_s) were recorded.

The coefficient of static friction (μ_s) was calculated using the formula: $\mu_s = F_s/N$, where F_s is the maximum static frictional force and N is the normal force.

For dynamic coefficient of friction, a 10 g normal force (N) was applied to the brake pad sample affixed to a sled. Then, the brake pad-sled assembly was tilted forward and backward to induce relative motion. Consequently, the resistive frictional forces (F_f) generated were measured. Simultaneously, the normal force, the applied load, the relative velocity, and the frictional forces were recorded over time. Using the recorded data, the dynamic coefficients of friction (μ) at various points during the test were calculated using the formula: $\mu = F_f/N$.

On the other hand, the wear rate was determined by adopting the method by Hanni et al., (2011). According to this method, each sample was clamped rigidly in position along the disc of the grinding machine for 60 seconds. The weight of each of the samples was measured before and after grinding. The difference in weight after the grinding process indicate the loss in weight.

Knowing the speed of the grinding machine and its disc diameter, the wear rate (W_r) was calculated thus:

$$W_r = \frac{\Delta W}{2\pi N R t} \quad (3)$$

Where ΔW = weight loss (g), R = radius of grinding disc (cm), N = speed in rpm (revolution per minute), t = time of grinding (i.e. 60 s).

Results and Discussion

Physico-chemical properties of cow hooves and bamboo fibre

FT-IR

The FT-IR results for the cow hooves and bamboo fibres are depicted Figure 1. From Figure 1(a), the N-H stretching vibration of the peptide bond (-CO-NH-) in the cow hooves could be observed at a wavelength 3267.24 cm^{-1} . Again, according to Kumawat et al., 2018, the FTIR absorption peaks at 1622.47 and 1531.93 cm^{-1} clearly indicate presence of amide I and amide II, respectively. Amide I is primarily associated with stretching vibration of C=O. The amide II is observed at the characteristic band of 1531.93 cm^{-1} and it is linked to the C-N stretching vibration and N-H bond bending within the protein structure (Yilma et al., 2022).

Figure 1: FT-IR spectra of pulverized (a) cow hooves and (b) bamboo fibres

On the other hand, the FT-IR test results for the pulverized bamboo fibre is given in Figure 1(b), while the extracted absorption values are listed in Table 1. Consequently, from the given results, the FTIR spectrum shows a large peak at 3338.85 cm^{-1} which is attributed to O-H stretching. The peak at 2881.75 cm^{-1} is linked to the C-H stretching, and the short peak at 1717.41 cm^{-1} represents the stretch of OH and C-H from the cellulose group. The absorption band at 1602 cm^{-1} represents the C=O functional group in hemicellulose and lignin. The absorption peak at 1503.79 cm^{-1} represents the aromatic C=C present in the lignin compound. The peaks in the range of $1233.77 - 1322.59 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ are associated to C-H deformation in cellulose and hemicellulose. The sharp absorption peak at 1032.24 cm^{-1} is linked to the C-O functional group present in cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. The absorption spectrum in the range of $455.11 - 525.73 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ represents the O-H out of plane bending.

Generally, from the Figure 1, the FT-IR absorption bands of cow hooves and bamboo fibres were extracted and presented in Table 1 for clarity.

Table 2: FT-IR absorption bands of pulverized cow hooves and bamboo fibres

Cow hooves			Bamboo fibres		
Peak No.	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	%T	Peak No.	Wavenumber (cm ⁻¹)	% T
1	3267.24	77.39	1	3338.85	89.50
2	2960.06	85.09	2	2881.75	97.29
3	1622.47	57.36	3	1717.41	92.14
4	1531.93	61.57	4	1602.48	91.55
5	1447.67	72.19	5	1503.79	92.97
6	1390.72	71.77	6	1322.59	90.37
7	1237.92	73.51	7	1233.77	87.16
			8	1032.24	70.70
			9	525.73	72.57
			10	51312	73.08
			11	499.94	73.45
			12	484.88	72.81
			13	472.57	72.53
			14	455.11	71.43

GC-MS

The GC-MS analysis chromatograms of cow hooves are depicted in Figure 2(a), and the twenty (20) chemical compounds found during the GC-MS analysis are listed in Table 2. The most prevalent chemicals as given in Table 2 are the alkanol-based compounds, followed by the alkanone- and alkane-based compounds. The other major compounds present in the cow hooves are the carboxylic acid and ester-based compounds. The presence of hydrocarbons, carboxylic acid, alkanols, esters, and ketone compounds among others in the GC-MS chromatogram of cow hooves confirms that cow hoof has self-lubricating oils which could help in the operation of brake pads. These observed chemical compounds are similar to those discovered by Okoroigwe et al., (2017) and Oyebanji et al., (2018).

Similarly, the GC-MS analysis chromatogram of bamboo fibres is shown in Figure 2(b), and the twenty (20) chemical compounds found during the analysis are equally listed in Table 2. Some of

these volatile compounds identified through the GC-MS analysis belong to the family of alkanols, acids, esters, aldehydes, and ketones. Thus, the presence of these volatile chemical compounds in bamboo fibres is a testament that bamboo fibre has the capacity for self-lubricating functionality.

Figure 2: GC-MS chromatogram of pulverized (a) cow hooves and (b) bamboo fibres

Table 3: GC-MS peak report for cow hooves and bamboo fibres

Peak #	Cow hooves			Bamboo fibres		
	Retention time(min)	Area	Name of constituent	Retention time(min.)	Area	Name of constituent
1.	3.041	2594244	2-Aminoimidazole-5-propionic acid	3.045	1015478	2-Pentene, 4-Bromo-
2.	5.566	21602	1,1,1 -Trifluoro-2-propanol	14.935	27102	Pentanedioic acid, 3-thioxo-, diethyl ester
3.	6.573	22051	2-Octanol, (S) -	15.915	17196	Cycloheptanol, 2-chloro-, trans-
4.	7.326	17175	3-Nonyl - 1 - ol	16.025	9494	Acetamide, 2-(4-morpholylcarbonylmethyl)thio-N-phenyl-
5.	9.829	27858	3-(Methylthio) pent-4-yn-1-ol	16.150	12362	1-[N-Aziridyl]propane-2-thiol
6.	10.897	26254	6,9,12-Octadecatrien-1-ol	16.285	23951	Cycloheptanol, 2-chloro-, trans-
7.	13.390	20751	Cyclohexanone, O-methyloxime	16.475	6718	1-Octanesulfonyl chloride
8.	14.265	23476	Gentamicine a	17.010	211725	Acetamide, N-methyl-N-[4-[4-fluoro-1-hexahydropyridyl]-2-butynyl]-

9.	15.000	124948	Tricyclo [5.1.0.0(3,5)]octane-2, 6-dione, 1,3,5,7-tetramethyl -	17.195	319547	2-Hydroxyethyl hydrogen vinylphosphonate
10.	15.206	174525	Glutaric acid, 3-(2-methoxyethyl)nonyl propyl ester	17.300	376573	4H-Thiopyran-4-one, 1,1-dioxide
11.	15.438	387967	Octanamide, N -(2 - mercaptoethyl) -	17.566	1150768	1,3,5-Triazine-2,4-diamine, N,N'-bis(1-methylethyl)-6-(methylsulfonyl)-
12.	15.550	227403	2-Butenoic acid, 2-methyl-, 4,4a, 5, 6, 7, 8, 8a,9-octahydro-8a-hydroxy-3,4a,5-trimethylnaphthol[2,3-b]furan-6-yl ester	17.743	2569215	Spiro[androst-5-ene-17, 1'-cyclobutan]-2'-one, 3-hydroxy-, (3.beta., 17.beta.)-
13.	15.985	1413263	2-Oxa-7-thiatricyclo[4.4.0.0(3,8)]decane	18.332	502808	Spiro[androst-5-ene-17, 1'-cyclobutan]-2'-one, 3-hydroxy-, (3.beta., 17.beta.)-
14.	16.195	1124798	8-Chloro-8-methyl-cis-8-silabicyclo[4,3,0]nonane	18.531	7450540	3-Methyl-4-(phenythio)-2-prop-2-enyl-2,5-dihydrothiophene 1,1-dioxide
15.	16.380	957411	1,3-Benzodioxole, 5-[1-[2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethoxy]butyl]-	18.895	1102011	4-Benzylpiperidine
16.	16.550	1072462	Undecane, 1,2,-dibromo-2-methyl-	18.971	1147891	2,3-O-Benzal-d-mannosan
17.	17.999	26709755	Spiro[androst-5-ene -17 ,1'-cyclobutane]-2'-one, 3-hydroxy-, (3.beta.,17.beta.)-	19.172	9976931	3-Methyl-4-(phenythio)-2-prop-2-enyl-2,5-dihydrothiophene 1,1-dioxide
18.	18.398	23514158	Ethy iso-allocholate	19.570	1470076	2,4-Dinitro-4'-methoxydiphenylsulfone
19.	18.982	9696729	Spiro [androst-5-ene-17,1'-cyclobutan]-2'-one, 3-hydroxy-, (3.beta., 17.beta)-	19.670	1242834	Tetraacetyl-d-xylonic nitrile
20.	19.302	19274091	Spiro [androst-5-ene-17,1'-cyclobutan]-2'-one, 3-hydroxy-, (3.beta., 17.beta)-	19.868	2675749	[1,1'-Bicyclopropyl]-2-octanoic acid, 2'hexyl-, methyl ester

Effect of varying proportions of cow hooves and bamboo fibres on the microstructural property of the fabricated brake pads.

Microstructural examination of brake pads is crucial for understanding their mechanical behaviour, wear resistance, and thermal stability. It helps to reveal the distribution or dispersion

of the filler materials plus other additives within the polymer matrix. Thus, the microstructural examinations of the brake pad samples are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 shows the microstructural examinations of the tensile fractured brake pad samples 01, 02, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7. A closer look at the sample 01 image reveals relatively good distribution of constituent materials. However, a void was observed which was due to pull off during tensile fracture. From the sample 02 microstructural image, a closer observation shows presence of the white-coloured particles and yellow-coloured undispersed bamboo fibres could be noticed. Again, one can see presence of undispersed white lumps of fillers, most likely to be Al_2O_3 which have the propensity to make the sample amenable to high water and oil absorption.

Sample 1 presents brake pad formulation with both cow hoof and bamboo fibres in the ratio of 8:2 (cow hoof: bamboo fibre). A closer look shows a relatively compact surface with the constituent materials fairly distributed. The water and oil absorption decreased significantly when compared with Sample 02. Sample 2 presents formulation with a little increase in the proportion of bamboo fibre and decrease in the amount of cow hoof when compared to sample 1. As expected, the water absorption increased marginally.

The microstructural image of sample 3 with cow hoof to bamboo fibre ratio of 6:4, and the microstructural image of sample 4 with equal proportion of cow hoof and bamboo fibre appear to exhibit similar surface properties. However, the marginal difference in percent water absorption could be due to higher amount of bamboo fibre in sample 4 compared to sample 3. The microstructural image of sample 5 with cow hoof to bamboo fibre ratio of 4:6 revealed a surface that is compact but have a few voids. However, it was observed that the percent water absorption was low. The reason could be that the inner structure of the sample was densely compact and thus relatively impervious to water.

With further increase in the amount of bamboo fibre and reduction in the quantity of cow hoof, the water absorption surged a little in sample 6. This could be due to increase in the amount of cellulose content of bamboo fibre. Then, sample 7 having cow hoof to bamboo fibre ratio of 2:8 shows a micrograph that revealed much presence of the bamboo fibres. The bamboo fibres were also observed to be unevenly distributed. Notably, the water absorption was found to increase, even though marginally. This is due to high presence of bamboo fibres.

Figure 3: Microstructural examinations of the tensile fractured brake pad samples 01, 02, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, & 7.

Effect of varying proportion of cow hooves and bamboo fibre on the physical properties of the fabricated brake pads.

Density

Determining the densities of the fabricated brake pads is crucial because it correlates directly with a brake pad's hardness, wear resistance, coefficient of friction, and overall structural integrity. Thus, a higher density generally leads to increased hardness and better wear resistance, while influencing friction and preventing crumbling under pressure and heat. However, the density of natural filler-based brake pads can vary significantly depending on the specific natural fibres and resins used, but generally falls within a range comparable to or even exceeding that of traditional asbestos-based brake pads, with reported densities ranging from approximately 1.0 to 2.5 g/cm³ (Ngwaba & Aikhuele, 2023).

Therefore, the densities of brake pad samples as graphically depicted in Figure 4 show that they are higher than 1.0 g/cm³, meaning that all the brake pad samples fall within the acceptable range. However, sample 6 with cow hoof to bamboo fibre ratio of 3:7 exhibited the highest density of 1.375 g/cm³.

Figure 4: Densities of the fabricated brake pads

Water and oil absorption

The values of water and oil absorbed by the fabricated brake pad samples are clearly presented in Table 3. From the results in Table 3, the brake pad sample 02 with only bamboo fibre as filler material exhibited higher water (7.810 %wt.) and oil (8.720 %wt.) absorptions compared to sample 01 with only cow hoof as filler material which displayed very low water (0.781 %wt.) an oil (0.324 %wt.) absorptions. Considering the effect of varying proportion of cow hoof and bamboo fibre, sample 7 with higher proportion of bamboo fibre than cow hoof gave the highest water and oil absorptions. The reason is that bamboo fibres have many hydroxyl (–OH) groups, and thus are hydrophilic in nature. Therefore, the sample 7 that has very high proportion of –OH groups tend to show low moisture resistance. This is in agreement with Dhakal (2007) who posited that the maximum water uptake increased as the natural filler content increased.

Table 4: Percent water and oil absorptions by the fabricated brake pad samples

Sample ID	01	02	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Water Absorption, % wt.	0.781	7.810	0.935	1.314	0.954	1.077	0.799	1.617	1.709
Oil absorption, %	0.324	8.720	0.386	0.898	1.418	1.005	0.794	0.891	2.022

Figure 5: Plots of (a) water absorption and (b) oil absorption by the fabricated brake pads

Tribological properties of the fabricated brake pad samples

Coefficient of friction

The coefficient of friction of a brake pad determines its effectiveness in gripping the brake disc to slow or stop a vehicle. A higher coefficient of friction means a better grip and thus shorter stopping distances and faster deceleration, but can also lead to increased wear. A lower coefficient of friction results in a weaker grip, longer stopping distances, and potentially more brake fade, but may offer greater durability. Therefore, appropriate coefficient is crucial for safety, as it dictates the stopping power of the brakes under various conditions, including different temperatures and speeds. During determination of coefficient of friction, both static coefficient of friction and dynamic coefficient of friction were considered. Hence, the static coefficient of friction measures the friction between surfaces that are not moving relative to each other, specifically the force required to initiate motion, while the dynamic coefficient of friction measures the friction between surfaces that are moving relative to each other. Thus, the coefficient of friction (CoF) for brake pads typically ranges from 0.3 to 0.5 for standard street pads, while performance and racing pads can have a CoF between 0.4 and 0.6, or even higher for specialized racing applications (Kshirsagar and Khairnar, 2022).

Therefore, Figure 6 presents results of the static and dynamic coefficients of friction. From the given results, the brake pad sample 01 with only cow hoof as filler material gave higher static coefficient of friction value of 0.521 compared to the sample 02 with only bamboo fibre as filler material which gave the value of 0.367. On the other hand, the dynamic coefficient of friction for sample 01 is 0.482 and was observed to be higher than sample 02 which is 0.318. Considering the effect of varying proportion of cow hoof and bamboo fibre, both the static and dynamic coefficients of friction increased from sample 1 to sample 6, and then showed a marked decrease with sample 7. However, generally, the obtained values of coefficient of friction fall within the given range already documented in the literature.

Figure 6: Graphical representation of the coefficients of friction. Blue colour = static coefficient of friction (CoF), and red colour = dynamic coefficient of friction (CoF).

Wear rate

The wear rate test for brake pad linings is a crucial assessment used to determine the durability and longevity of brake pad linings under simulated conditions of friction and heat. This test provides insights into how much material is lost from the brake pad lining during braking, which directly correlates to the lifespan of the brake component. The rate of wear is critical for understanding how long a brake lining will last under normal operating conditions and how often it will need to be replaced. A low wear rate indicates that the brake lining material is durable and will have a longer service life, whereas a high wear rate suggests that the material may degrade quickly, necessitating more frequent replacements. Hence, Figure 7 presents values of wear rate test for the fabricated brake pad samples. From the given results, the brake pad sample 01 with only cow hoof as filler material gave highest value of wear rate (2.504E-08 g/m) compared to the sample 02 with only bamboo fibre as filler material which gave the value of 1.952E-08 g/m.

Considering the effect of varying proportion of cow hoof and bamboo fibre, sample 7 with higher proportion of bamboo fibre than cow hoof gave the lowest wear rate (1.026E-08 g/m), suggesting that the brake pad sample would be most durable with the longest service life compared to other samples. The reason the brake pad sample with higher proportion of bamboo fibre exhibit lower wear rate is due to the fibrous nature of bamboo which allows it to create more coherent and stable wear layers plus the inherent structural characteristics of bamboo fibre, which include higher mechanical properties, better durability, and a greater capacity for forming stable frictional contact surfaces with the brake disc. Whereas the sample with high proportion of cow hooves displayed

higher wear rate because the organic composition of cow hooves is more prone to fragmentation, leading to higher rates of wear particle generation and a less durable friction interface.

Figure 7: Plot of wear rate versus sample ID

Conclusion

The effects of varying proportions of cow hooves and bamboo fibres on the microstructural, physical and tribological properties of fabricated brake pads have been investigated. In respect of the microstructural properties, sample 1 presents brake pad formulation with both cow hoof and bamboo fibres in the ratio of 8:2 (cow hoof: bamboo fibre), which shows a relatively compact surface with the constituent materials fairly distributed. The distribution of constituent materials in samples 2,3 and 4 were found to be uneven. The micrograph of sample 5 with cow hoof to bamboo fibre ratio of 4:6 reveals a surface that is compact but have a few voids. The micrograph of sample 6 revealed a relatively compact structure, while the sample 7 having cow hoof to bamboo fibre ratio of 2:8 shows a micrograph that revealed much presence of the bamboo fibres observed to be unevenly distributed. The densities of brake pad samples show that they are higher than 1.0 g/cm^3 , meaning that all the brake pad samples fall within the acceptable range. However, sample 6 with cow hoof to bamboo fibre ratio of 3:7 exhibited the highest density of 1.375 g/cm^3 . The sample 7 with higher proportion of bamboo fibre than cow hoof gave the highest water and oil absorptions. The reason is that bamboo fibres have many hydroxyl ($-\text{OH}$) groups, and thus are hydrophilic in nature.

Considering the effect of varying proportion of cow hoof and bamboo fibre on the tribological properties of the fabricated brake pad samples, both the static and dynamic coefficients of friction increased from sample 1 to sample 6, and then showed a marked decrease with sample 7. However, generally, the obtained values of coefficient of friction fall within the given range already documented in the literature. With respect to wear rate determination, sample 7 with higher proportion of bamboo fibre than cow hoof gave the lowest wear rate ($1.026\text{E-}08 \text{ g/m}$), suggesting

that the brake pad sample would be most durable with the longest service life compared to other samples.

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